

Additional Appendix to Rodríguez Del Pino (2025)

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ABSTRACT

This is an additional appendix to: *GA-NIFS: high prevalence of dusty and metal-enriched outflows in massive and luminous star-forming galaxies at $z \sim 3 - 9$*

Appendix C: Kinematic maps

In this section we present, for each system in our sample, the maps of line fluxes and kinematics obtained from the emission-line analysis (of $[\text{O III}]\lambda 5007$ or $\text{H}\alpha$) described in Sec. 3.1 from Rodríguez Del Pino 2025. We include maps of integrated line fluxes, velocity and velocity dispersion for the one-component fit (top) and the narrow (middle) and broad (bottom) kinematic components. These maps, in particular the ones displaying the velocity and velocity dispersion of the broad component, are used to define the regions hosting ionized outflows, which are highlighted in red, as in Fig. 4 from Rodríguez Del Pino (2025).

Appendix D: Spectral modeling of outflow spectra

This section contains the spectral modeling of the integrated spectrum of the outflows identified in our sample of star-forming systems, including the main emission lines identified in each case. When an emission line is better modeled with two kinematic components (see Sec. 5 from Rodríguez Del Pino (2025)) we show narrow (blue) and broad (red) components, otherwise we only show the one-component model (green).

Fig. C.1: Maps of integrated line fluxes, velocity and velocity dispersion for the one-component fit (top), narrow kinematic component (middle) and broad kinematic component (bottom) for 23170. The outflowing region is highlighted in red in the bottom panels.

Fig. C.2: Same as Fig. C.1 for 5001.

Fig. C.3: Same as Fig. C.1 for 4891.

Fig. C.4: Same as Fig. C.1 for HFLS3_g1.

Fig. C.5: Same as Fig. C.1 for HZ4.

Fig. C.6: Same as Fig. C.1 for HZ10.

Fig. C.7: Same as Fig. C.1 for 12306.

Fig. C.8: Same as Fig. C.1 for HFLS3_w.

Fig. C.9: Same as Fig. C.1 for CR7.

Fig. C.10: Same as Fig. C.1 for COS30.

Fig. C.11: Same as Fig. C.1 for SPT0311, although in this galaxy we do not identify an outflow.

Fig. C.12: Same as Fig. C.1 for B14, although in this galaxy we do not identify an outflow.

Fig. C.13: Same as Fig. C.1 for MACSJ0416-Y1.

Fig. C.14: Same as Fig. C.1 for EGSY8P7.

Fig. C.15: Same as Fig. C.1 for MACS1149-JD1.

Fig. D.1: Spectral modeling of the main emission lines present in the integrated spectrum of the ionized outflow identified in 23170. Green lines correspond to the total best-fit. When the profile of an emission line is better modeled with two kinematic components (see Sec. ??) we also display the narrow and broad components as blue and red lines, respectively. Residuals shown in the bottom panels are obtained by subtracting the best-fit model to the data points.

Fig. D.2: Spectral modeling of the main emission lines present in the integrated spectrum of the ionized outflow identified in 5001. A description of the panels is provided in Fig. D.1.

Fig. D.3: Spectral modeling of the main emission lines present in the integrated spectrum of the ionized outflow identified in 4891. A description of the panels is provided in Fig. D.1.

Fig. D.4: Spectral modeling of the main emission lines present in the integrated spectrum of the ionized outflow identified in HFLS3_g1. A description of the panels is provided in Fig. D.1.

Fig. D.5: Spectral modeling of the main emission lines present in the integrated spectrum of the ionized outflow identified in HZ4. A description of the panels is provided in Fig. D.1.

Fig. D.6: Spectral modeling of the main emission lines present in the integrated spectra of the ionized outflows identified in HZ10_E (top) and HZ10_W (bottom). A description of the panels is provided in Fig. D.1.

Fig. D.7: Spectral modeling of the main emission lines present in the integrated spectrum of the ionized outflow identified in the nuclear region of 12306. A description of the panels is provided in Fig. D.1.

Fig. D.8: Spectral modeling of the main emission lines present in the integrated spectra of the ionized outflows identified in HFLS3_w 1 (*top*) and (*bottom*). A description of the panels is provided in Fig. D.1.

Fig. D.9: Spectral modeling of the main emission lines present in the integrated spectra of the ionized outflows identified in CR7_a (top) and CR7_b (bottom). A description of the panels is provided in Fig. D.1.

Fig. D.10: Spectral modeling of the main emission lines present in the integrated spectrum of the ionized outflow identified in the nuclear region of COS3018. A description of the panels is provided in Fig. D.1.

Fig. D.11: Spectral modeling of the main emission lines present in the integrated spectrum of the ionized outflow candidate identified in the nuclear region of B14. A description of the panels is provided in Fig. D.1.

Fig. D.12: Spectral modeling of the main emission lines present in the integrated spectrum of the ionized outflow identified in MACSJ0416-Y1. A description of the panels is provided in Fig. D.1.

Fig. D.13: Spectral modeling of the main emission lines present in the integrated spectrum of the ionized outflow identified in EGSY8P7. A description of the panels is provided in Fig. D.1.